

ANALYSIS OF A SQUEEZE-INFILTRATION PROCESS FOR

FABRICATION OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Summary

Melt infiltration of a fibrous preform is an attractive fabrication route for metal matrix composites. The equipment described here is designed to allow the various mechanical and thermal phenomena which take place during the process to be monitored with some precision. Experimental data are presented for injection of aluminium-based melts into preforms composed of fine δ -alumina fibre with a silica binder. These measurements are examined in conjunction with analyses of the sources of resistance to melt flow, the mechanical response of the preform, the heat transfer characteristics and the solidification behaviour of the alloy. It is concluded that typical conditions involve considerable compression of the preform prior to melt penetration, followed by rapid melt infiltration and a subsequent relaxation of the preform back to its undistorted shape, provided this is not inhibited by passage of the solidification front. Microstructures are shown which illustrate the sequence of events. Some recommendations are made about practical approaches to the elimination of process instabilities and structural defects in this type of fabrication route.

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1. Introduction

The squeeze-infiltration route is now attracting considerable interest as a commercial method of making metal matrix composites. Several patents have recently been published, with Japanese involvement becoming very pronounced(1-6). There has, however, been little published which is aimed at process analysis, although some related processes have been examined(7-9). The current authors have recently published(10) a paper describing the salient features of the process being considered here. This has been termed Pressure-Assisted Network Infiltration to form Composites (PANIC).

Much of the recent interest has centred around the use of alumina fibres; in particular, a fine δ -alumina fibre has been developed by Imperial Chemical Industries plc specifically for metal matrix composites applications, known as "Saffil" RF (reinforcement) grade. Composites manufactured using the PANIC process on preforms of this fibre have been found to exhibit high degrees of structural perfection and very strong fibre/matrix bonding. It has been shown(11) that the interfacial structure of these composites approximates very closely to the ideal case of a physical continuum and chemical discontinuum. Certainly, although the physical contact is highly intimate, no evidence has been found suggesting any interfacial chemical reaction, (with the exception of slight penetration of magnesium into a few atomic layers on the fibre surface, which was observed in some cases). This situation is in contrast to that with other fabrication routes (using other fibres), in which, for example, wetting may be difficult to achieve or formation of thick interfacial reaction layers may be a common feature(12,13).

However, optimization of the structure obtained by PANIC processing requires an understanding of the exact sequence of events. For example, the fibre distribution in the composite may differ from that in the preform, with local variations in volume fraction appearing in a way that is confusing at first sight. A similar type of defect sometimes appears in the form of regions where the preform has apparently undergone delamination in places. Finally, there are wide ranges of conditions under which the melt will fail to infiltrate successfully, particularly with a fine fibre such as that being considered here (3 μ m diameter). Although considerable progress has been made on a trial-and-error basis, it is an appropriate time to attempt to place the process in a useful analytical framework.

2. Process Description

The equipment is illustrated schematically in Fig. 1. The die in current use has a diameter of 100 mm and a depth of about 120 mm. This allows preforms of up to about 30-40 mm thickness to be infiltrated without encountering problems of melt overflow prior to entry of the ram into the die. (The melt depth needs to be greater than the preform thickness at this stage if the entire preform is to be successfully infiltrated.) The melt is preheated to a selected superheat and introduced into the launder via a bottom pouring arrangement. (This avoids problems associated with the incorporation of dross.) After rotating the launder away from the cavity area, the ram is then lowered into the die (at a velocity of about 9 mm s⁻¹) and the pressure allowed to build up as infiltration takes place. The hydraulic system is a simple one, with which a cut-off pressure is preselected, and the build-up to this is dependent on the resistance encountered by the ram.

The die and base are initially brought to some appropriate temperature, in order to avoid premature chilling of the melt. The ram is also preheated, by prior introduction into the die cavity. The preform is

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of the experimental set-up

introduced into the die a short period before pouring, and is itself raised to a temperatures close to that of the die. The preform is a fairly tight fit into the die cavity, to reduce the danger of premature melt penetration into the periphery, trapping pockets of air within the preform. After infiltration, the preselected pressure is maintained for a period of a minute or so, by which time the solidification is believed to be complete. The system is then normally left for a further short period, before retracting the ram, with the composite billet attached to the dovetail. The billet is then simply removed with gentle lateral pressure.

In addition to the nature of the thermal field, the successful operation of the process depends on the existence of suitable air escape paths from the cavity region. These are furnished in the present equipment by dimensioning the die and base plug to provide a peripheral gap suitable for escape of air (but too small to allow significant subsequent penetration of liquid metal). The structure of the preform is also of importance in terms of the nature of the product, although it has been found that successful infiltration can be achieved with a wide range of fibre volume fraction and binder levels. All the preforms referred to here exhibit a fibre distribution which approximates to a random planar array.

3. Process Analysis

3.1 Preform Penetration

Resistance to melt penetration at the surface of the preform arises from the effect of enforced meniscus curvature. This is described by the familiar Kelvin equation

$$\Delta P_{\#} = 2 \gamma \sum_i \frac{1}{r_i} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta P_{\#}$ is the pressure drop across a surface (the subscript # refers to the infiltration front) exhibiting principal radii of curvature r_i , and γ is the interfacial energy. The curvatures imposed depend on the volume fraction f_{fib} , radius r_{fib} and distribution of the fibres. Also relevant is the assumption made about the degree to which fibre/melt wetting at the front reduces the curvature. If, as seems probable, wetting is insufficiently rapid to allow any curvature relaxation over the timescale of the infiltration, the minimum radius imposed corresponds to twice the inter-fibre spacing and the following expressions are obtained for different types of fibre array

$$\Delta P_{\#,1} = \frac{2\gamma}{r_{fib}[(\pi/4f_{fib})^{1/2} - 1]} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta P_{\#,2} = \frac{4\gamma}{r_{fib}[(\pi/2f_{fib})^{1/2} - 1]} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta P_{\#,3} = \frac{4\gamma}{r_{fib}[(3\pi/4f_{fib})^{1/2} - 1]} \quad (4)$$

these referring to a one-dimensional bundle, two dimensional square mesh and three-dimensional cubic array, respectively. Using the value(14) of 0.84 J m^{-2} for γ of aluminium, the behaviour predicted by these equations for fibres with the dimensions of "Saffil" is shown in Fig. 2. These curves suggest that the excess pressure necessary to initiate (and continue) infiltration of a relatively dense network ($f_{fib} \approx 0.2-0.4$) is of the order of ten atmospheres ($\approx 1 \text{ MPa}$). Alloying tends to reduce the value of γ somewhat so that the figure might be correspondingly lower for melts containing appreciable solute levels. These pressures are modest for a process involving a ram, but high for gas pressurization techniques; in particular, simple vacuum infiltration would appear to be unacceptable. However, the curve for a fibre radius of $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ shows that the pressure increment from this source should be considerably less with coarser fibres.

3.2 Preform Infiltration

A second source of resistance to infiltration is expected after initial penetration. This arises from frictional forces experienced by liquid flowing through interstitial channels and is dependent on the flow velocity and infiltration distance. This resistance is described by the Blake-Kozeny equation(15), which in the present case gives the following expression for the pressure gradient in the melt necessary to generate a given flow velocity, u

$$\frac{dP}{dz} \approx 16.8 \left[\frac{f_{fib}}{r_{fib}(1-f_{fib})} \right]^2 u \eta \quad (5)$$

where η is the dynamic viscosity of the melt ($\approx 10^{-3} \text{ Pa s}$ for aluminium). This equation is valid only for laminar flow and the onset of turbulence(16) (expected for a packed-bed Reynolds number higher than 2) is predicted for pressure gradients greater than a critical value

Figure 2 - Predicted dependence of the pressure drop across the infiltration front on the volume fraction of fibre, for penetration of an aluminium melt into different types of fibrous array.

$$\frac{dP}{dz_{crit}} \approx 67.2 \left[\frac{f_{fib}}{r_{fib}(1-f_{fib})} \right]^3 \frac{n^2}{\rho} \quad (6)$$

where ρ is the density of the melt.

The pressure gradients necessary to generate flow at three different velocities are shown as a function of f_{fib} for a 1-D bundle of ($3\mu\text{m}$ diameter) fibres in Fig. 3, together with the boundary representing the onset of turbulence and a curve for a coarser fibre. If we are considering an infiltration depth of the order of a few tens of millimetres, it may be inferred that (for f_{fib} values up to about 30%) the pressure increment necessary to generate sufficiently rapid flow to complete infiltration in about a second is no more than about ten atmospheres (the corresponding velocity and pressure gradient values being about 30 mm/s and 40 kPa/mm). This pressure increment would be considerably lower for coarser fibres. The corresponding analyses are not available for 2-D and 3-D arrays of fibres, but in general less resistance to flow is expected for these cases (at a given volume fraction of fibre). It would thus appear likely that pressure development in the melt during the PANIC process is such as to ensure that infiltration, once initiated, will be completed very rapidly. This presupposes that there is no generation of back-pressure ahead of the infiltration front, such as might arise with inadequate air escape paths.

Figure 3 - Predicted variation with volume fraction of fibre of the pressure gradient necessary to generate flow of an aluminium melt through a fibrous bundle at different velocities.

3.3 Preform Deformation

In view of the information above, pressures of up to around a few tens of atmospheres might be necessary to infiltrate the preform. It is obviously of interest to know how the preform itself is likely to respond to such stresses. This is very difficult to predict accurately as a function of fibre properties, distribution and local constraint (imposed by the characteristics and level of the binder). However, the mechanical properties of the preform do tend to vary in a consistent manner with fibre volume fraction and binder level, for given types of fibre and binder. For example, Fig. 4 shows experimental data for compression of preforms in the die with no melt present. The compressive strains at which damage occurs have also been measured; typically, fibre fracture may start at a relatively low strain, but damage does not become catastrophic until the preform has been compressed by more than about 50%. It may be noted that, if infiltration requires pressures of the order of ten atmospheres (1 MPa), this will be associated with appreciable prior compression of the preform ($\approx 30\%$), but this can be largely accommodated by elastic deformation and need not incur excessive fibre breakage. An important characteristic under these circumstances is the local relaxation behaviour of the preform after passage of the infiltration front (and a consequent dramatic fall in the local pressure gradient). In particular, it turns out that the rate of relaxation under those circumstances is expected to play a significant rôle. Unfortunately this property is a difficult one to obtain, either theoretically or by experimental measurement. This is particularly so as the relaxation characteristics required are those when the compressed

Figure 4 - Stress-strain data for preforms with three different initial volume fractions of fibre, for dry deformation within the die.

structure is surrounded by a relatively viscous medium under high hydrostatic pressure. Difficulties in estimating a characteristic relaxation time under these conditions for a given preform constitutes the major obstacle to the completion of a model relating processing conditions to composite structure.

3.4 An integrated process model

Although development of the model is incomplete, the sequence of events to be simulated is becoming clear. The phenomena involved take place essentially along the vertical axis, although the peripheral regions are important in maintaining this unidirectionality by allowing air escape but not melt penetration. Sequential pressure and fibre volume fraction profiles are illustrated schematically in Fig. 5 for times corresponding to the start of preform compression (t_0), the start of infiltration (t_1), the completion of infiltration (t_2) and the start of solidification (t_3). The small pressure P_0 is that necessary to move the ram freely in the die (expelling the air from the cavity). The pressure drop at the infiltration front $P_{\#}$ will depend on the local volume fraction of fibre in the manner shown in Fig. 2. In addition to these events, a solidification front will at some stage start to advance from the contact surface with the ram. The growth of these two solidification fronts will depend on the material and starting temperature of base and ram, the surface finish of these (as it affects the interfacial heat transfer coefficients) and the composition and prior superheat of the melt.

Figure 5 - Schematic illustration of the changing profiles of fibre volume fraction and pressure during the process.

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The approach to modelling this complex combination of processes is to examine the sequential variation of the spatial position and local fibre fraction of a series of points within the preform, together with the pressure and temperature profiles. The changing position of the preform surface, infiltration front, ram/melt interface and solidification front are shown schematically in Fig. 6, together with the corresponding fibre fractions and the pressure at the ram. This latter variable may be continuously monitored, as may the ram position, but the other parameters are

Figure 6 - Schematic illustration of the development of fibre fraction, pressure and axial position of selected reference points.

not easy to measure directly. (The temperature distribution is, however, accessible experimentally and this must be measured if the boundary conditions are to be fully specified.) The dotted line shows the changing position of some arbitrary point within the preform, moving with the local fibre network. The (circled) points of intersection of this line with the $z_{\#}$ and z_{*} plots represent this location in the preform being passed by the infiltration front and the solidification front respectively.

The mechanical behaviour of the system may be modelled independently of the thermal and solidification characteristics. However, it is by combining the two sets of predictions that the most useful information is likely to emerge. The thermal modelling can be carried out by standard techniques(17,18), particularly as convective heat transfer can probably be neglected. The main uncertainty concerns preform relaxation, as this may constitute a significant heat transfer mechanism once a thermal gradient has been established. An indication of the type of prediction obtained if it is

Figure 7 - Predicted thermal histories for points within the preform and at the surface of the die base under selected conditions.

neglected is given in Fig. 7, these data being obtained from a finite difference model. This figure gives thermal histories at the base surface and at a point within the preform, which may be compared with the experimental data shown in Fig. 9. These curves are based on a constant fibre fraction of 40% and a constant heat transfer coefficient at the melt/base interface of $20 \text{ kW m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$. This latter value is of the order expected for the case of high pressure contact. Agreement with experiment could have been improved by allowing the value of h to fall as solidification occurred at the interface, but such refinements are probably not justified at this stage. The initial melt temperature is less than T_p ($=800^\circ\text{C}$) as a result of the (very rapid) local heat transfer to the fibre and some allowance for heat losses between pouring and infiltration.

The mechanical modelling is complicated by the rather complex boundary conditions. The following may be identified:

1. Conservation of fibre volume

$$f_{\text{fib},0} z_{\text{sur},0} = f_{\text{fib},\#} z_{\#} + \int_{z_{\#}}^{z_{\text{sur}}} f_{\text{fib}} dz \quad (7)$$

2. Conservation of melt volume

$$(z_{ram,o} - z_{sur,o}) = (z_{ram} - z_{sur}) + \int_{z_{\#}}^{z_{sur}} (1 - f_{fib}) dz \quad (8)$$

a correction for the freezing contraction may also be applied.

3. Relationship between infiltration velocity, local fraction of fibre and local pressure gradient
- see equation (5)
4. Relationship between pressure drop at the infiltration front and local volume fraction of fibre
- see equations (2) - (4)
5. The mechanical response of the preform to applied stress. This would have to be obtained by experimental measurement.
6. The relaxation behaviour of the preform after release of an applied stress. This is not only very difficult to predict theoretically, but also presents severe problems for experimental measurement under the conditions of interest.

Subject to the successful implementation of these boundary conditions, it should be possible to describe the process fully. This would, for example, allow prediction of the conditions required to avoid local variations in volume fraction of fibre in the composite. Although the overall complexity should not be underestimated, the completion of such a model should be possible in the near future.

4. Process Monitoring

In order to shed light on the sequence and timescale of the various events, simultaneous logging of thermal, pressure and displacement data have been carried out. Displacement of the ram was measured via a rigid arm impinging on an extended-travel transducer and the pressure in the hydraulic system was also recorded. Sheathed chromel-alumel thermocouples of 1 mm diameter were placed at preselected positions along the system axis. Logging was carried out with an Apple II microcomputer. As an example, Fig. 8 shows data from a run with a commercial purity aluminium melt. The thermocouple was embedded flush with the surface of the die base and the sharp rise evident at about 1.7 s corresponds to arrival of the infiltration front. It can be seen that this occurs a very short time after the rise in pressure necessary to initiate melt penetration into the preform. It is also evident that the displacement data are consistent with this in that ram movement undergoes a sharp transition from almost unhindered motion (at about 9 mm s^{-1}) to virtual complete arrest within this regime. (The ram actually continues to move down slowly as a result of thermal and solidification contraction.)

Figure 8 - Experimental data for temperature (at the surface of the die base), pressure (in the hydraulic system) and ram displacement during infiltration with an aluminium melt of a preform containing 18% by volume of fibre and 5% by weight of silica binder. The zero points on the scales of time and displacement are arbitrary.

The conclusion that infiltration is very rapid is also consistent with data such as those of Fig. 9. This shows the result of a similar logging run with an Al-10wt%Mg alloy, using a thermocouple protruding into the preform, in addition to one embedded at the base surface. As expected, passage of the infiltration front caused a very sharp response from the thermocouple in the preform: the next integration of the signal from the second thermocouple was completed less than 0.1 s later and by this time the temperature at this point had already risen considerably. In fact, if the data are analysed carefully, the lower limit for the infiltration velocity cannot strictly be placed at more than about 15 mm s^{-1} , although it seems probable that the actual velocity is considerably greater. This would be consistent with the pressure data and the analysis presented in section 3.2. It should be easy to verify this with faster logging and ultra rapid-response thermocouples.

Figure 9 - As for Fig. 8, for an Al-10wt%Mg alloy. Thermocouple 1 protruded into the preform about 5.5mm above the base, while thermocouple 2 was embedded flush with the base surface.

The sequence of events proposed in section 3.4 is also consistent with certain microstructural evidence. For example, differential compression of the fibre distribution has been noted, giving structures such as those shown in Fig. 10. This shows local fibre volume fraction varying from about 40% near the base to the nominal initial value of around 18% near the top surface. This is believed to result from the solidification front from the die base passing regions where local fibre relaxation is incomplete. Local increases in fraction of fibre have also been observed near the periphery of some billets, presumably as a result of such premature solidification being enhanced by lateral heat flow.

Figure 10 - Optical micrographs from a single Al-10%Mg-18vol% fibre composite: transverse sections taken at heights of approximately (a) 15 mm, (b) 10 mm and (c) 5 mm above the die base.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

A process has been described which is attracting considerable attention as a fabrication route for metal matrix composites. In commercial practice, interest is centred on the selective incorporation of fibrous preforms into certain regions of die castings. While these may have a complex geometry, the current work has concentrated on a simple unidirectional situation. However, even with this simplification, a complete description of the process represents a considerable challenge for the methods of mathematical modelling. Although a unified model remains to be fully implemented, considerable progress has been made towards clarifying the roles of the various thermophysical phenomena which can affect the product structure.

The present work is concerned with preforms composed of a random planar array of a fine alumina fibre, sized to give a typical length of about 500 μm , and held by a silica binder in a configuration giving a fraction of fibre which can be preselected in the approximate range of 5-30% by volume. Infiltration of these preforms by a superheated aluminium melt requires the generation of a significant pressure. The magnitude of this pressure depends on a number of factors, but both theoretical analysis and experimental data suggest that a typical figure might be about 10-20 atmospheres (1-2 MPa). Once initiated, infiltration of the preform is believed to take place very quickly, with the melt front passing through a preform 20 mm thick in a fraction of a second.

The pressures necessary to complete this infiltration are also sufficient to compress the preform considerably, a typical figure being a strain of perhaps 30%. This is largely achieved by elastic deformation of individual fibres, so that, once infiltration is complete, the fibre structure might be expected to relax back to its undeformed state, leaving the fibre distribution in the composite essentially the same as that of the preform. However, a major uncertainty surrounds the rate at which this relaxation occurs when the fibres are surrounded by liquid metal under a high hydrostatic pressure. If the rate of relaxation is relatively low, the fibre packing at a given point may still exceed the nominal relaxed value when it becomes essentially fixed by passage of a solidification front in the matrix. This can lead to variations in local volume fraction of fibre within a single composite billet. Further information on the details of relaxation behaviour might allow tailoring of preform structure or solidification behaviour (for example, by control of heat transfer coefficient values). In summary, the process involves a complex interplay of transport phenomena, which merit further attention if the technique is to be fully optimized.

NOMENCLATURE

Parameters

f	volume fraction
D	thickness of preform (m)
h	heat transfer coefficient ($W m^{-2} K^{-1}$)
P	pressure (Pa)
r	radius (m)
t	time (s)
T	temperatures (K)
u	infiltration velocity ($m s^{-1}$)
z	axial distance (m)
γ	interfacial energy ($J m^{-2}$)
η	dynamic viscosity (Pa s)
ρ	density ($kg m^{-3}$)

Subscripts

fib	fibre
p	pouring
sur	preform top surface
ram	ram lower surface
#	infiltration front
*	solidification front (from base)

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